

Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE)

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for personalized medicine

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Communication and public engagement plan

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Executive summary

This CISTEM communication and public engagement plan (CPEP), deliverable included in work package 3, provides an overview of the strategy, activities and materials that CISTEM intends to use in order to improve communication, dissemination and public engagement over the course of the project.

This first deliverable is the baseline and will be reviewed and updated at least one time during the project development. Update will contain an evaluation of the communication activities undertaken during the previous period; an updated version of the general communication strategy; and detailed planning for the period ahead; Although the main goals will remain, some of the proposals could be modified, and new actions could be suggested when necessary.

In addition to this document, dissemination actions and tools to reach specialized researchers, technologists, industrial actors and policy makers are compiled in the CISTEM Dissemination and Exploitation Plan and updates.

1. Introduction

The CISTEM communication and public engagement plan involves communication and dissemination activities that are linked to the general public, instead of the research and industrial communities directly linked with the research activities of the project. The instruments that form the communication and public engagement strategy for the project are described in this report.

CISTEM participants will be engaged in communication and dissemination activities through the CISTEM CPEP. They will communicate with the general public through the social media accounts (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn), through the website, as well as through conferences, workshops and thus reach a much wider research population.

Furthermore, press releases will be issued and/or other information leaflets including posters will be prepared. One of the main objectives for the CISTEM project is to maintain high visibility and to encourage the participants to present their project to a wide audience.

1. CISTEM communication objectives

The main goal behind the communication and public engagement actions is to contribute to the societal awareness of the new technological results and activities developed by the CISTEM project including organ-on-chip, microfluidic and stem cell biology. To do so, the CPEP will schedule different actions aiming to reach general audiences beyond the scientific and industrial communities.

The specific objectives of the communication and outreach plan are:

- Project knowledge: actions to raise awareness about the project
- Promotion of project outcomes: actions to announce new results, new publications and patents, attendance to specific events (workshops, fairs, congress...)
- Dissemination: public disclosure of the progress and results of the project
- Education: increasing public awareness of the societal benefits of the project involving youngsters and students in science events
- Promote of the Marie Curie Skłodowska-Curie Actions and Horizon 2020 among the whole society with particular emphasis on young researchers, university and high school students.

2. Target audience

In order to attain the previous goals, CISTEM project will target different group of stakeholders and other public by using a tailored dissemination and communication approach specific to each group. This will ensure a customized presentation of the project, as well as relevant uptake by the target audience and will substantially increase CISTEM's impact. The target audiences that the communication actions aim to reach are divided in the following groups

- The clinical end-users and health care practitioners, patients' organizations
- National, regional and local health authorities and policy makers;
- The industrial stakeholders interested in the uptake of the new knowledge and technology produced, including associations of diagnostic and medical device industries; patients

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- Academic and scientific community: young researchers, students, schools, research centers and institutes (visibility of project output);
- Society as a whole

In the following table it is possible to identify the target audiences and the communication tools more adequate for each of them:

Table 1: Overview of CISTEM communication strategy

Target audience	Communication tool					Key messages
	website	Social network	Printed material	Events	Press coverage	
practitioners, patients' organizations		Advances on scientific knowledge, knowledge applications within the microfluidic and stem cell discipline				
EC and Policy makers		General progress of the project - Legislation, standardisation and development issues				
The industrial stakeholders		- Optimized working conditions: cost reduction, scalability and efficiencies - New market opportunities, especially for the drug discovery, personalized medicine				
Academic and scientific community		Advances of the project and potential applications of the obtained results				
Society as a whole		Advances of the project and potential applications of the obtained results in personalized medicine- Alternative to animal testing.				

3. Tools, Channels and Activities

3.1. Visual identity

A distinct, clear and easily recognizable visual style is arguably crucial to the achievement of CISTEM communication objectives since it will reflect strong and distinctive values of the CISTEM ecosystem.

3.1.1. CISTEM logo

The CISTEM logo is the visual element that represents the project and promotes instant public recognition. The logo was designed with a simple and dynamic look directly related with the goal of the project, reflecting heart pulse inside a frame representing a microfluidic device.

Figure 1: CISTEM logo

The CISTEM logo will be present on all materials related to communication, together with the EU emblem, a direct statement on the funding source and the Grant Agreement number

Figure 2: EU logo

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3.1.1. Template

A minimalistic but clear documentation templates containing layout and styles designed for the project will be used to create standardized documents and ensure a unified corporate image. So far the following resources have been created:

- Logo (in various versions)
- PowerPoint template
- Word deliverable and report template

Additional templates will be designed by the communication Manager as needed in the frame of project activities.

3.2. Digital channel promotion

CISTEM digital channels include: website and social media

3.2.1. CISTEM website

The website is a central pillar for the project’s interaction with the public and so a determined effort has been made to present information in a manner that can be understood by members of the public. The project’s website, www.CISTEM-project.com, launched in January 2018, is considered as the right channel to communicate about the projects and its activities, events and then, to reach multiple audiences scientific and not. The website also provides contact details for all project partners to facilitate cooperation and knowledge sharing within and beyond the Consortium. All other communication channels and means will lead the audience to the website, which will hold updated information about the project according to its progress. It will also contain links to relevant information available elsewhere such as publications, presentations, etc. As such it offers public one-stop access to information about the project’s background, activities, ambition and result.

Figure 3: main page of the CISTEM’s website

3.1.2. Social networks

Social networking has become mainstream in enhancing active citizen participation, engagement and collaboration over the internet. CISTEM will take full advantage of the most used and effective

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social networks to maximize its communication and public engagement. Social media, unarguably, will provide a treasure trove of longer-run benefits for CISTEM, including but not limited to:

- Encouraging open dialogue with the different target groups
- Gaining brand recognition & proactive reputation management by showing that CISTEM is a dynamic and active project
- Fostering genuine conversations with the target audience

Social media dissemination has started from M1. Three main social channels have been chosen for this means: LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook (See table below). They will be linked to social networks that are already in existence within the consortium to reach a broad audience. Posts will include new results published on the website, training and networking activities, workshops conferences, events, and news regarding organ-on-chip, stem cell biology and microfluidic innovation.

Table 2: social media used for CISTEM communication and dissemination

	LinkedIn		
Feature	- logo and a cover image - short description - link to the website	- logo - short description - link to the website	- logo and a cover image - short description - link to the website
Content	-Training and networking activities -Workshops, news and events related to the project. - Link to mini review about the project topics	-Training and networking activities - Workshops, news and events - News about organ on chip, microfluidic and stem cell biology innovation in the private and academic sector	- Intelligence and insights regarding organ-on-chip technologies - Relevant CISTEM cluster news, events, workshops and conferences and outcomes
Objectif	- Make organ-on-chip technology and its impact on personalized medicine more readily intelligible and widely known. - Raise public interest in science and to the fact that new technologies like organ-on-chip can lead to benefits for society and individuals - To Promote the MSCA and H2020 among the whole society	- Interact with the public by following, re-tweeting and favoriting with key audience groups and projects that are present on Twitter - Consolidate and build the community of organ-on-chip by the use of relevant hashtags (example: @organonchip). - To Promote the MSCA and H 2020	- To strategically connect and professionally engage with CISTEM target groups - To consolidate and build the community of organ-on-chip Bring on board new relevant stakeholders - Disseminate the main project outcomes

3.2. Offline Communication

3.2.1 Events

A key part of the public engagement and communication efforts are project events and external events that provide excellent opportunities to disseminate project activities, objectives and results to the target communities and then to impact positively awareness-raising regarding CISTEM project. Indeed, active participation at external events (conferences, workshops, symposia, fairs) is crucial to CISTEM' dissemination strategy as it allows direct contact with the audience scientific or not with which the project wishes to engage.

CISTEM participants expect to be involved in a variety of event formats, ranging from conferences and workshops to fair trades and exhibitions, and to take on all tasks related to event planning and implementation and supporting the project with dissemination material (brochures, poster). The consortium members will also organize workshops jointly with worldwide conferences and well-known events on specific topics.

➤ *CISTEM events*

Three joint events will be organized during the project either directly managed by the project, or co-organized and with other relevant international/national initiatives. The events will take place in:

- a) Novi Sad (Serbia)- the first workshop is planned to be organised by BioSense Institute end of March 2019 to present the project results and activities.
- b) Krakow (Poland)-the second Workshop will be held in Krakow from 23-25th September 2019 during the 7th Eurobioetch conference where a special session on organoids and organs-on-a-chip will be organized by CISTEM participants (University of Krakow)
- c) Novi Sad (Serbia)- the final event will be organized by BioSense Institute in the last year of the project to present the project results and activities.

The dissemination team will promote the events/workshops/sessions organised or co-organised by CISTEM on the project website, the Social Media, LinkedIn relevant groups

➤ *Non-CISTEM events*

Members of the consortium are committed to encourage the investigators to engage with the public and the stakeholder by having exhibition in science festivals and events in order to raise the status of the different technologies used in the CISTEM project in Europe. This concerns mainly participation in trade fairs, congresses, EU organized events as well as open days and visits in school and specific training. This channel will provide information tailored to targeted audiences. The interactive channels will be the most efficient means for community building and has the highest impact on communication. Participation in several events is already planned (Table 3):

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Table 3: Non-CISTEM events

Name	Target group	Objectives
European Researcher night - 2018, 2020	- Students - Young researchers - Experienced researchers (ER)	1) Raise the awareness of the CISTEM project outcomes and activities 2) Educate wider audience student 3) Promote the value of integrated and cross-disciplinary skills and expertise 4) Promote the MSCA-RISE and the opportunities that it offers in - Developing career of young researchers in research - Giving to Europe the chance to gain competitiveness in key research fields.
International festival of science and education - Novi Sad (Serbia) - May 2019, 2020, 2021	- Students - Young researchers - ER - Citizen - School pupil	1) Raise the awareness of the CISTEM project outcomes and activities 2) Educate wider audience student 3) Promote the value of integrated and cross-disciplinary skills and expertise 4) Promote the MSCA-RISE and the opportunities that it offers in - Developing career of young researchers in research - Giving to Europe the chance to gain competitiveness in key research fields.
The EuroScience Open Forum (ESOF) - July 2020	- Students - Young researchers - ER - Business actors - Policy makers - Journalists	1) Raise the awareness of the CISTEM project outcomes and activities 2) Educate wider audience student 3) Promote the value of integrated and cross-disciplinary skills and expertise 4) Promote the MSCA and the opportunities that offer RISE action in - Developing career of young researchers in research - Giving to Europe the chance to gain competitiveness in key research fields.
European Conference on Corporate R&D and Innovation CONCORDi	- Students - Young researchers - ER - Policy stakeholders - Market leader companies - European business associations	1) Raise the awareness of the CISTEM project outcomes and activities 2) Educate wider audience student 3) Promote the value of integrated and cross-disciplinary skills and expertise 4) Promote the MSCA-RISE and the opportunities that it offers in - Developing career of young researchers in research - Giving to Europe the chance to gain competitiveness in key research fields.
iSEC - SMART & SAFE CITIES FAIR - Belgrade (Serbia) - 2019, 2018	- Companies - SMEs - Business actors - Policy makers - Journalists	1) Establish a network with the main academic and industrial partners across Europe involved in microfluidic, organ on chip and medicine sector. 2) Raise the awareness of the CISTEM project outcomes and activities especially regarding: - the cutting-edge technologies project that provide CISTEM project - The potential that offers microfluidic and organ on chip for rare disease investigation and precision medicine

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International Conference on Rare Diseases and Orphan Drugs (ICORD)	- Researchers from academic and industry - Patient organisations - Regulatory authorities - Health authorities - Public policy professionals	1) Establish relationships with Patient representatives and Healthcare professionals to achieve a mutual understanding of the solutions being developed and explore possibilities offered by microfluidic and organ-on-chip technologies. 2) Promote the MSCA and the opportunities that offer RISE action 3) Establish contact with potential users from Industry of the knowledge and solutions developed by the CISTEM project and explore possibilities of knowledge transfer and valorization of solutions. 2) Raise the awareness of the CISTEM project outcomes and activities especially regarding - the cutting-edge technologies project that provide CISTEM - The potential that offers microfluidic and organ on chip for rare disease investigation and precision medicine
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3.2.2. Printed materials

Diverse types of promotional material will be designed for print. When possible, this material will also be available in digital form. Partners will be invited to share this promotional material on every suitable occasion, thus putting CISTEM directly in the hands of the right set of target audience.

➤ *Poster*

Two poster versions presenting the expertise and services of CISTEM has been prepared (Figure 4) to be used for exhibition in various events (conferences, workshops etc.) for dissemination purposes. They are available in English and Serbia and include project and EU logos. The poster will be updated at later stage of the project by highlighting success stories and results.

Figure 4: CISTEM'poster presented at a) Researcher'Night 2018 in Novi Sad (Serbia) and b) Casamansun 2018 workshop in Senegal (Afrique)

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➤ Brochure

A first project brochure comprises a double-sided leaflet, available in English and Serbia as well, with a clean, modern and attractive design presents the project logo and various information on the project including project's website, project's partners, the programme under which it has been funded, the logo of the European Union and information on the project's background and the solution provided by CISTEM applications

Figure 5: CISTEM Brochure

3.3. Media releases

Press releases can be another tool to promote the project and the benefits to the organization from the MSCA action. In addition, opportunities of broadcasting (TV or radio) interviews will be pursued to bring at a high level, the knowledge, achievements and importance of the scientific domain of CISTEM. Throughout the lifespan of the project significant breakthrough accomplishments and events will be identified and sent to online and offline communication media. For example: <https://horizon-magazine.eu>, <http://horizon2020projects.com/publications/>.

4. Conclusions

This Deliverable includes the communication and public engagement plan of the CISTEM project, providing the main guidelines tools, channels and activities for the widespread diffusion of project vision, activities and results and to reach and engage distinct target groups. To this aim, the main target groups are identified and a broad range of potential communication and dissemination activities have been defined to increase the awareness and stimulate interest in the project technologies and achievement